

4-SHO‘BA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA

CLASSIFICATION OF DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS IN HR MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: Modern society is characterized by market relations and a high degree of globalization, which implies a huge number of organizations. Human capital is one of the main resources of an organization. Since today an employee is not just a performer, but a strategic resource of the company, investing in which will give a competitive advantage. This article considers the classification of decision support systems in personnel management systems.

Key words: personnel management, DSS, personnel resource, OLAP, data analysis.

Personnel potential is of particular importance in the context of the development of a market economy. Thus, there are new requirements for managing the use of human resources. Modern companies set themselves the goal of maintaining the stability and development of business in a highly competitive environment.

Today, it is very important to search for effective forms and methods of using human resources to ensure sustainable economic growth. Under the management of human resources in the enterprise, will be understood as ways to maintain and maintain the motivation of staff in the enterprise. One of the main problems is that it is difficult for managers to determine the psychological and emotional state of each employee under their supervision. As a result, employees with insufficient or excessive motivation appear. But do not forget that it also depends personally on each employee, as well as on the stage of his development at the enterprise [1, p.96].

At present, the very direction of the decision support system (DSS) can be divided into several classes, which have acquired functionality and now lead an independent life. These areas include ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) - systems, BI (Business Intelligence) - systems [2, p. 35].

The main task of the DSS is to provide a decision maker with a tool to perform data analysis. It should be noted that for the effective use of DSS, its user-analyst must have the appropriate qualifications. The system does not generate correct solutions, but only provides the analyst with data in the appropriate form (tables, reports, graphs, etc.)

for study and analysis. The DSS should help the decision maker answer questions like "What happens if...". The word "support" says that systems only help management make decisions, understand the situation, but do not replace them [3, p. 93].

Approaches to building a DSS, whether methodological or technological, are based on the implementation of an iterative, multi-stage decision-making process, including the following steps: analyzing trends and visualizing dependencies found in data using data mining tools and OLAP technologies, identifying structural features in data obtained in during data monitoring. The central element integrating the basis of the entire decision-making procedure in such systems can be a generalized simulation model of the object of study, implemented in the DSS based on a complex of interrelated simulation and optimization models [4, p. 157]. Based on the scenario approach, a selection procedure is implemented and is characterized by the direct participation of an expert in a modeling study and the use of an experimental computer modeling approach in combination with various analytical methods. These include: statistical methods, iterative, logistic, balance, simulation-optimization computational procedures [5, p. 28].

The exponential growth in the amount of data currently being analyzed, the increased requirements for the speed of analysis, as well as the complexity of describing the machine form of data representation, are spurring research and development of intelligent DSS. Such DSS are distinguished by the presence of functions that implement individual mental tasks of the decision maker.

According to the method of support, there are:

1. Model-based DSS, search for optimal solutions based on specially developed models (statistical, financial, etc.);
2. Data-driven DSS organize user support in finding effective solutions by aggregating large amounts of data from heterogeneous sources;
3. Knowledge-oriented DSS searches for optimal solutions based on a specially developed knowledge base.

According to the degree of “intelligence” of data processing during analysis, three classes of analysis tasks are distinguished:

1. information retrieval - performs requests predefined in the system. The analyst does not have the ability to create custom queries;
2. operational-analytical - allows you to summarize the data, as well as grouping in the form required by the analyst. A distinctive feature of information retrieval analysis is the impossibility of predicting the queries required by the analyst, i.e. a mechanism for executing user requests is needed;

3. intellectual - with a certain probability predicts the development of some processes, based on the found logical and functional patterns [6, p.512].

Figure 1. DSS architecture.

Subsystems for input and storage of information in different systems do not differ much, but the analysis subsystem is the main part of the DSS, which determines its effectiveness and uniqueness, so this subsystem needs to be studied in more detail.

It can be concluded that the introduction of such an automated system will allow HR managers to reduce staff turnover, due to information about the potential desires of employees to leave the organization, and timely response to them.

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